

The Sequence of Acquisition in Pienemann's Processability Theory

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Abstract

The study of how languages are acquired has always brought a vast number of variables into the path of investigation, shedding light on the mystery of this phenomenon. In the present literature review, we focus on language acquisition in a systematic order, where a specific sequence is implicated to support the process-oriented approach to structural points of a language. We also separate the opponents of acquisition first into cognitive approach, pedagogical role, and physiological facets regarding the views of experts. Then, we allocate the major part of the study to introduce the model of Pienemann called Processability Theory. The introduction of the theory includes different associated sections that have been truly discussed in detail based on developmental stages, universality, and processing constraints. What is the main aim of this literature review is to find the relation between the acquisitional sequence in Pienemann's processability theory which is done thoroughly in four main sections: 1. Developmental readiness, 2. Hierarchical processing, 3. Morpho-syntactic mapping, 4. Transfer of processing skills.

Keywords: Acquisition, Cognitive approach, Developmental, Hierarchical, Morpho-syntactic, pedagogical, physiological, Pienemann's processability theory, processing, Transfer, universality.

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Definition of acquisition

Morphological and syntactic growth are the key concepts of language acquisition according to Roger Brown (1970s). Furthermore, the developmental flow of acquisition appears over time and through learning grammatical and syntactical structure (Brown 1973) the thing which is opposed to Chomsky's viewpoint. According to Noam Chomsky (1960s), acquisition is considered as an internal capacity of every human being in which they are able to learn a new language as well as their mother tongue.

Different factors are related to acquisition; specially when it comes to environmental aspects in which a new language is being acquired (Skinner 1957). So, the relation between language acquisition and environmental stimulus was considered as a crucial factor to get engaged with second language. On the other hand, Krashen (1981) pointed out that there is no need for interaction to acquire a new language, but the exposure with linguistics input.

Larsen-Freeman (1997) also emphasized the dynamicity of language acquisition in the way that second language development is not happened in a straightforward path, but follows a complex, adaptive, and non-linear system. Her

assertion gets importance due to the organization of learner's mind; although interaction and social points are considerable, they will reach self-organization over time and be adapted to new linguistic data and communicational needs.

Cognitive approach

The cognitive approach plays a vital role in the stage of second language acquisition. In the process of acquiring a new language, the inner world of the learner is a focal facet rather than the world outside them (Chomsky 1950s). The emergence of the Language Acquisition Supporting System (LASS) is against Chomskian theory; according to LASS, both nurture and nature are key features in second language acquisition (Bruner 1983).

Chomsky's viewpoint is twofold: Nativism and Innatism. Innatism side tells us that no other species would be capable of learning a human language; besides, the innatism side shows that children internalize their mother tongue without any effort. Across the process of acquiring second language, a logical problem pops up in which we always produce language more than we hear it (Chomsky 1960s).

A broader perspective of Chomsky is against connectionism arguing that whatever we hear plays and shapes the patterns in our mind (Chomsky 1980s). The reason behind this phenomenon relies on the methodological contrast to the current

views of him e.g., Chomsky's Universal Grammar vs. Emerging Language from Neural-like Network and Experience.

Pedagogical role

The role of acquisition in the pedagogical area is well shown through different works such as Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) which is prominently focused on acquiring the language through doing a meaningful activity (Ellis 2003). Meaning-focused activities bring practical experience of language acquisition whereas they are rehearsed in purposeful conditions through using the target language (Swain 1985).

Language development can occur through social interaction. Vygotsky (1926) stated that there is gap between what learners can do alone and what they are able to do through receiving help from their higher levels such as teachers, classmates, families, and other stakeholders; the gap is well known as ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development). Accordingly, the more the gap gets closer, the sooner the learners reach autonomy. Of course, teacher is a mediator in this process.

The role of interaction is thoroughly highlighted by what Long (1991) has named it Interaction Hypothesis. Face to face interaction is significant to meet meaning negotiation due to the inclusion of comprehensible input, selective attention and feedback, and output modification. Cultural awareness is the other

side of social interaction in which learners communicate with foreigners or their friends from other regions in order to improve their language abilities (Oxford 1990).

Physiological facets

The other facet of language acquisition is rooted in Psychology; specially the branch related to psycholinguistics. The features of this stage are varied such as cognitive science in which the difference between implicit and explicit memory systems are clarified and divided into two different fields of attention: first, procedural memory which is grammar and fluency aimed; second, declarative memory using for vocabulary and rules (Paradis 1980s).

Neurolinguistics and aging are other key points in psychological facet. In fact, brain function is analyzed considering the factor of age and its effect on acquiring the second language (Opler 1987). Her study shows that the relation between vocabulary and released certain linguistic functions-effected by aging- is contrary; although aging slows down the functions, words and semantic become stronger.

Acquiring second language means to be able to talk and also understand the spoken language; the concept of bilingualism. Arturo E. Hernandez (1990s) investigated that how bilinguals acquire multiple languages and store them in the

brain. He found out the process of alternating between languages by bilinguals based on the context, audience, and emotion referring code-switching or the flexibility of language.

Processability theory

Many complicated grammar points are included in learning a new language. Furthermore, the knowledge that enables learners to predict and develop the sequence of language acquisition is based on the capability of brain to gradually process the complexity of structures (Pienemann 1998). Learners acquire grammar based on cognitive limitations in a fixed order.

The importance of step-by-step learning outweighs the instruction itself in the processability theory. The dependent relation between stages prevents learners to skip even one of them; the hierarchy of process (Pienemann 1998). In other word, the increasing process of grammatical difficulty prepares learners to completely understand the given structure then the other one.

The model of speech production presented by Levelt (1989) shows the transformation of thoughts into spoken form on a structural basis. Moreover, the ordered stage of this process includes conceptualization, formulation, articulation, and Self-monitoring must be implicated as well. Besides, the implication of

grammatical teaching matters especially when it comes to notice the learners' readiness of acquiring the point (Pienemann & Lenzing, 2020).

Processing Constraints

Straightforward usage of form-focused activities is considered as a main way of implementing grammatical teaching, but there are some limitations ahead; Pienemann explains it in this way:

“Learners can only produce linguistic forms for which the necessary processing procedures are available. For example, the ability to move constituents in a sentence (like in question formation) depends on the prior development of procedures for handling grammatical agreement”. (Pienemann & Lenzing ,2020, p. 140)

The other imposed constraint refers to the transformation of knowledge in the L2; it is visible in the case of although the existence of a point in the first language is obvious, the implication of it in the second language is not happened till the L2 processor analyzes it (Pienemann & Lenzing, 2020). It shows that the first language is directly constrained by the second language hierarchical model.

Language of learners is shaped through the superficial usage of second language which is called interlanguage and obviously it is varied among learners (Selinker, 1972). Some factors interfere in this phenomenon like fossilization,

variability, errors transformation, and so on. What is fortunate against this problem is the continuous exposure with the language to cope the process difficulties.

Developmental stages

Pienemann's processability theory has a central stage referring to the coherence of structural points in language acquisition in which grammatical features start from the basic and stage by stage get more complex under the shadow of the previous stage. Although the difficulty of the present structural point might be hard to cope with, the learner is not allowed to skip it (Levelt, 1989).

Surprisingly, developmental stage is the common stage between acquiring grammatical structures of a new language, regardless of the region of learners and notion of the language. In addition, the concept of linguistic validity represents the adaptability of language (Pienemann, 1989). Accordingly, effectiveness of instruction will be illustrated if the learners' readiness is notified that shows they are developmentally ready to catch the new points.

According to Pienemann and Lenzing (2020), the supportive explanation of the processability theory in producing language is divided into three main categories: 1. Hierarchical stages; chain-by-chain grammatical improvement, 2. Sequenced limitations; final well implemented production requires having

complete understanding of the previous point, 3. Developmental readiness; gradual complexity of grammatical structures.

Universal applicability

The concept of universality defines the cognitive role of processability theory rather than its linguistic functions. However, developmental sequences is considered as a key common notion between all languages despite being different in the form of structures and also geometric properties (Biase & Kawaguchi, 2012). In fact, PT is applicable in all language teaching areas due to its language independent stages.

The humanized construction of language processing causes the limitations as the whole common obstacles between language trainers (Biase & Kawaguchi, 2002). The accurate assessment can be provided across languages through the implication of PT as a tool to examine the learner's developmental structure-based knowledge.

The tendency of processability theory is to process-oriented rather than language-oriented category. Although, the mixture of capability of both learners and teachers are essential in structural acquisition, following and continued rehearsal are stressed in the learning path (Ericsson, 1993). Moreover, consistency in structural improvement accelerates the conceptual concrete understanding.

Developmental Readiness

In the case of linking process ability theory and language acquisition, developmental readiness is considered as a sign of psycholinguistic field which the acquisition placed in the background of language processing (Pienemann, 1998). Implication of teaching structures from simple to complex deepens the learners' structural perception.

When it comes to the real-time feedback from brain, the significant role of processing appears; it is truly related to the capability of mind reaction at a given domain, not for the basis of what is rehearsed or implicated (Williams et al., 2024). As a matter of fact, the brain and developmental readiness are interwoven and cannot be considered separate from each other.

The recognition of the exact structural forms is often possible alongside the final production of learners. For instance, the feasibility of producing a full-structured phrase before the enrichment of vocabulary knowledge comes to nothing (Kida & Barcroft, 2017). It means that, structural knowledge cannot stand alone unless the previous related stages (e.g., vocabulary improvement) have come to be completed.

Hierarchical Processing; Morpho-syntactic Mapping

Another magnificent relation between acquisition and processability theory is rooted in TOPRA model (Type of Processing-Resource Allocation); the more a type of process (e.g., grammatical) gets increased, the more reduction possibility in coming sections (e.g., word order) (Kida & Barcroft, 2017). In other words, essential stages must be completely done then the next complicated stages should come to the path.

The reinforcement order of acquisition is the final goal and main cooperation of processability theory and acquiring a new language in the way that learners first get prepared to improve their semantic depth then syntactic fluency come up to the path (Pienemann & Lenzing, 2025). Accordingly, different stages like lemma access and category procedure accelerate acquiring the lexical items in the field of semantic readiness.

Moreover, the more complicated facets such as subordinate clauses and correct structural follow ups are ready to be acquired in the field of syntactic fluency. Additionally, the order of morpho-syntactic mapping reinforcement is not considered as a fixed process, because it is directly related to the reaction of processing brain system in the real-time constraints; that is what gives the sense of cognitivism rather than pedagogical point of view (Tolentino & Tokowicz, 2011).

Transfer of Processing Skills

Skills are also transferred one after each other following a specific systematical order which is framed from declarative to procedural knowledge. Furthermore, the continuous exposure and involvement with the target content enables the brain to automate the application of rules (Pienemann, 1998). The formulation of the skills transformation occurs whereupon the structural encoding automation.

The transformation of skills in a systematic process-oriented path starts from conceptualization (what to say) in which both meaning and experience are structured specifically in the case of language production or comprehension (Jiang & Yang, 2021) to formulation (how to say) where language is formed and ends in articulation where the language is ready to be produced based on the elaboration of physical muscles (Levelt, 1989).

Conclusion

Through the revision of this study, the importance of sequencing in language acquisition appears as the essential factor in the processing stage of the language learning in the way that cognition and individualized characteristics are interwoven. Furthermore, the order of skills is taken place in a logical sequence in which the achieved skill is completed then the next ones pop up after each other. The capability of acquiring new language requires the learners' readiness in all aspects of cognition; for instance, language acquisition will never be happened if there is no mind readiness of learners. However, schemata activation straightforwardly is depended on the applicability of teachers in the given domain. Additionally, the sequence of acquisition becomes a reflection of the underlying cognitive architecture rather than a product of pedagogical sequencing. As learners progress through stages—from lexical to phrasal, and eventually to clause-level processing—they gradually gain the capacity to handle more complex syntactic operations, such as subordinate clause embedding or feature unification. This developmental constraint explains why certain structures resist early acquisition despite frequent exposure: they simply exceed the learner's current processing threshold. Thus, Processability Theory provides a robust explanatory framework

for the observed order of acquisition, aligning linguistic development with psycholinguistic processing capacity. Alongside the mentioned points in this study, the findings must be used with caution; there might be other factors in this field which has not been considered yet.

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